

Peer Tutoring Learning Model as A Strategy to Improve Motivation and Learning Outcomes of Chemistry Education Students in The Early Stages of Study

Elferida Sormin

Chemistry Education Department, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Kristen Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of the peer-to-peer learning model as a strategy to improve the motivation and learning outcomes of chemistry education students in the early stages of study. The background of this study is based on the low learning motivation and academic achievement of first-year students who are still in the adaptation stage to the learning environment in higher education. The peer-to-peer model was chosen because it is able to create a collaborative, communicative learning atmosphere and supports active student involvement. This study employs a quantitative approach with a pre-experimental design, specifically a one-group pretest-posttest design. The research sample consisted of 15 chemistry education students in the early stages of the study who were selected by purposive sampling. The research instruments included a learning motivation questionnaire and a learning outcome test that had been tested for validity and reliability. Data analysis was carried out descriptively and inferentially using the N-gain calculation to determine the level of improvement. The results showed that the average score of students' learning motivation in the pretest was 62.4, increasing to 82.7 in the posttest, with an N-gain value of 0.54, which is included in the moderate category. Meanwhile, the average student learning outcome in the pretest of 58.6 increased to 85.2 in the posttest with an N-gain value of 0.64, which is included in the moderate to high category. This increase indicates that the implementation of the peer guidance model can significantly increase student motivation and conceptual understanding. The conclusion of this study is that the peer guidance learning model is effective in increasing the motivation and learning outcomes of chemistry education students in the early stages of study. This model is recommended as an innovative learning strategy that can be implemented in higher education to support the academic success of new students.

KEYWORDS: peer tutoring, learning motivation, learning outcomes, N-gain, chemistry education

I. INTRODUCTION

Higher education plays a strategic role in producing quality human resources, particularly in science education, such as chemistry education. Chemistry education students are expected not only to master chemistry concepts in depth but also to possess strong pedagogical skills to become future professional educators. However, in the early stages of their studies, students often face various challenges, such as difficulty adapting to the academic environment, low motivation to learn, and limited understanding of abstract and complex chemistry concepts. These conditions can impact student learning outcomes if not addressed with appropriate learning strategies (Caspersen et al., 2017; Nurhawa et al., 2024). Motivation to learn is a crucial factor influencing student academic success. According to John W. Santrock (2018), motivation to learn acts as an internal driver that drives individuals to achieve learning goals. Students with high motivation tend to be more active, persistent, and have better learning strategies than those with low motivation. Motivation to learn is closely related to the use of cognitive and metacognitive strategies, which contribute to improved learning outcomes. Therefore, efforts to improve motivation to learn are crucial in the learning process in higher education (Chiu et al., 2023; Felea & Roman, 2023; Filgona et al., 2020).

On the other hand, student learning outcomes are also an important indicator in assessing the success of the learning process. Learning outcomes not only reflect mastery of the material but also demonstrate the effectiveness of the learning methods used. However, conventional teacher-centered learning often fails to encourage active student engagement. This leads to students becoming passive and less motivated to participate in the learning process (Amin et al., 2018; Fadillah, 2016; Metekohy et al., 2022). Therefore, innovations in learning models are needed that can increase active student participation and encourage more meaningful interactions. One approach that can be used is the peer tutoring learning model. This model is a form of collaborative learning in which students help each other understand the learning material. Learning involving social interaction can help individuals reach a higher level of understanding through the concept of the zone of proximal development (ZPD). In this context,

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peer tutors act as more capable peers who provide support (scaffolding) to their peers (ARENDALE, 2025; Montanero et al., 2025)

Recent research shows that the peer tutoring model has a positive influence on student motivation and learning outcomes. A study by Topping demonstrated that peer tutoring is effective in increasing student learning engagement, self-confidence, and academic achievement (Topping, 2026). Furthermore, research by Roscoe and Chi confirmed that the activity of explaining material to others (learning by teaching) can strengthen conceptual understanding and improve long-term retention (Roscoe & Chi, 2007). Other research has also found that students involved in collaborative learning have higher levels of motivation compared to those who learn individually (Caspersen et al., 2017). In the context of chemistry education, the application of the peer tutoring model is becoming increasingly relevant given the complex nature of chemistry material that requires in-depth conceptual understanding. Discussions between students allow for conceptual clarification, misconception correction, and strengthening of understanding through diverse perspectives. Furthermore, the more relaxed and informal learning environment of peer tutoring can reduce the learning anxiety often experienced by students in the early stages of their studies (Arco-Tirado et al., 2020; Montanero et al., 2025).

However, the implementation of the peer tutoring model remains suboptimal in many universities, particularly in chemistry education study programs. Many learning processes are still dominated by lecture methods, thus underutilizing the potential for interaction between students. Therefore, research is needed to examine the effectiveness of the peer tutoring learning model as a strategy to increase student motivation and learning outcomes, particularly in the early stages of study (Felea & Roman, 2023; Renninger & Hidi, 2019; Wardani et al., 2020). Based on this description, this research is crucial to provide alternative solutions for improving the quality of learning in higher education. By examining the influence of the peer tutoring learning model on the motivation and learning outcomes of chemistry education students, it is hoped that more effective, innovative learning strategies can be developed that meet the needs of students in the modern education era.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Peer Tutor Learning Model (Peer Tutoring)

The peer tutoring learning model is a form of collaborative learning that involves students as both tutors and tutees in the learning process. In this model, students with a better understanding of the material help their peers grasp learning concepts. According to Keith J. Topping, peer tutoring is an effective learning strategy because it involves two-way interaction that can improve conceptual understanding, communication skills, and student engagement (Topping, 2026). The concept of peer tutoring is based on the social constructivism theory proposed by Lev Vygotsky (1978), which emphasizes that learning occurs through social interaction. This theory recognizes the concept of the zone of proximal development (ZPD), which is the distance between an individual's actual abilities and the potential development that can be achieved with the assistance of more competent peers. In the context of peer tutoring, students act as learning facilitators, providing scaffolding to their peers. Furthermore, according to Fu & Hwang, collaborative learning such as peer tutoring can increase positive interdependence, promotive interactions, and individual accountability within a group. This makes learning more meaningful and student-centered (Fu & Hwang, 2018).

Recent research also shows that peer tutoring is effective in improving students' learning outcomes and social skills. Roscoe and Chi (2020) stated that the activity of explaining material to others (learning by teaching) can strengthen conceptual understanding and increase long-term retention (Roscoe & Chi, 2007).

Characteristics of the Peer Tutoring Model

The peer tutoring learning model has several key characteristics, namely:

1. Student-centered learning. Students are active in the learning process, both as tutors and tutees.
2. Intensive social interaction. Two-way communication occurs, enabling discussion and clarification of concepts.
3. Collaborative learning. Students work together to achieve shared learning goals.
4. Dual student roles. Students can act as both tutors and learners.
5. Supportive learning environment. The learning atmosphere is more relaxed and less stressful than conventional learning.

Advantages of the Peer Tutoring Model

The peer tutoring model has several advantages, including:

- Improving conceptual understanding through active discussion
- Increasing student motivation and self-confidence
- Developing communication and social skills
- Creating a more enjoyable learning environment
- Assisting students in the academic adaptation process
- Research shows that peer tutoring is effective in improving learning outcomes and student engagement because it provides opportunities for active and collaborative learning (Topping, 2026).

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Disadvantages of the Peer Tutoring Model

Despite its many advantages, this model also has several limitations, such as:

- Dependence on the quality of peer tutors
- Potential for conceptual errors if the tutor lacks understanding of the material
- Requires good planning and supervision
- Not all students have good teaching skills

Therefore, training and guidance are necessary for tutors to ensure optimal learning.

Peer Tutoring Relationships, Motivation, and Learning Outcomes

The peer tutoring learning model is closely linked to improved student motivation and learning outcomes. The social interactions that occur within peer tutoring can increase learning engagement, ultimately impacting learning outcomes. According to social constructivism theory, learning that involves interaction between individuals will produce deeper understanding than individual learning (Arco-Tirado et al., 2020; Nardacchione & Peconio, 2022).

Furthermore, peer tutoring also supports increased learning motivation through a more relaxed, communicative, and non-pressurizing learning environment. Students tend to feel more comfortable asking questions and discussing with peers than with lecturers. This can increase self-confidence and active participation in learning.

Empirical research shows that peer tutoring has a significant positive influence on student motivation and learning outcomes. Topping stated that peer tutoring not only improves academic achievement but also students' social skills and self-confidence (Topping, 2026). This is supported by research by Roscoe and Chi, which showed that the process of explaining material to others can significantly improve conceptual understanding.

Thus, it can be concluded that the peer tutor learning model is an effective strategy in increasing student motivation and learning outcomes, especially in the early stages of study which require academic adaptation support.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study used a quantitative approach with a pre-experimental approach. The design used was a one-group pretest-posttest design, involving one group of subjects who were given an initial test (pretest), then given treatment in the form of a peer tutoring learning model, and concluded with a final test (posttest). This design aimed to determine changes before and after the treatment.

Schematically, this research design can be depicted as follows:

$$O_1 \rightarrow X \rightarrow O_2$$

Where:

O_1 = Pretest

X = Treatment (peer tutoring learning model)

O_2 = Posttest

Research Location and Time

This research was conducted on students in the Chemistry Education Study Program at a university. The study was conducted in the first semester of the current academic year.

Population and Sample

The population in this study was all chemistry education students in the initial stage of their studies. The research sample consisted of 15 students selected using a purposive sampling technique, with the criteria being active students in the first semester taking related courses.

Research Variables

The variables in this study consist of:

- Independent variable: Peer tutoring learning model
- Dependent variable:
 1. Student learning motivation
 2. Student learning outcomes

Research Instruments

The instruments used in this study include:

1. Learning Motivation Questionnaire

This questionnaire was used to measure student learning motivation based on the Attention, Relevance, Confidence, and Satisfaction (ARCS) indicators. The scale used was a Likert scale with a range of values 1–5.

2. Learning Outcome Test

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This test was used to measure students' cognitive abilities in understanding chemistry material. The test consisted of multiple-choice questions tailored to the learning indicators.

Before use, the instrument was tested for validity and reliability to ensure its suitability as a research measurement tool.

B. Data Analysis

The Hypothesis Analysis by the paired sample t-test

The paired sample t-test was carried out to find out whether the independent variable, namely the practicum learning method, has a significant effect on the dependent variable, namely student learning outcomes. The t test applied is the right side t test.

1. Gain Test

Gain score calculation aims to find out how to increase student learning outcomes. Classification index gain as follows:

Table 1. Classification Index Gain

Gain Score	Interpretation
0.71 - 1.00	High
0.31 - 0.70	Middle
0.1 - 0.30	Low

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Result

This study involved 15 chemistry education students at a private university in Jakarta. In the initial phase of the study, the peer tutoring model was implemented. Data collected included student learning motivation scores and learning outcomes before (pretest) and after (posttest) the treatment.

The analysis showed an increase in student learning motivation. The average learning motivation score in the pretest was 62.4, which then increased to 82.7 in the posttest. Based on the N-gain calculation, the value obtained was 0.54, which is considered moderate. This indicates that the peer tutoring model provides a fairly effective contribution to increasing student learning motivation. Student learning motivation was measured using several indicators: (1) attention to learning, (2) learning relevance, (3) self-confidence, and (4) learning satisfaction. The following are the average pretest, posttest, and N-gain scores for each indicator, as presented in Table 2:

Table 2. Student Learning Motivation Score per Indicator

No	Indicator	Pretest	Posttest	N-gain	Category
1	Attention	63,2	83,5	0,55	Middle
2	Relevance	61,8	81,9	0,52	Middle
3	Self-Confidence	60,5	82,3	0,55	Middle
4	Satisfaction	64,1	83,1	0,53	Middle
Mean		62,4	82,7	0,54	Middle

Furthermore, student learning outcomes also experienced significant improvement. The average pretest learning outcome score of 58.6 increased to 85.2 in the posttest. The N-gain value was 0.64, which falls into the moderate to high category. This improvement indicates that students' conceptual understanding of the chemistry material taught improved after the implementation of the peer-to-peer learning model.

The analysis results show significant improvement, as shown in Table 2 below:

Table 3. Student Learning Outcomes

No	Variable	Pretest	Posttest	N-gain	Category
1	Leraning Outcomes	58,6	85,2	0,64	Middle-High

Table 4. Summary of Improved Motivation and Learning Outcomes

Variable	Pretest	Posttest	N-gain	Category
Learning Motivation	62,4	82,7	0,54	Middle
Learning Outcomes	58,6	85,2	0,64	Middle-High

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Based on the research results, all learning motivation indicators increased after the implementation of the peer-to-peer learning model. The attention and self-confidence indicators showed the highest increase with an N-gain of 0.55, while the relevance indicator had the lowest increase with an N-gain of 0.52, although all remained in the moderate category.

This improvement indicates that the peer-to-peer learning model is able to encourage active student engagement, increase self-confidence in learning, and provide a more meaningful learning experience. Furthermore, the increase in learning outcomes with an N-gain of 0.64 indicates that students not only experienced increased motivation but also improved conceptual understanding.

Overall, the results of this study indicate that the peer-to-peer learning model is effective in improving both the affective and cognitive aspects of chemistry education students in the early stages of their studies.

Hypothesis Analysis Test

The hypothesis analysis used a paired sample t-test. This was conducted to determine the difference in mean scores between the pretest and posttest after implementing the peer tutoring learning model. The results of the paired sample t-test are presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Paired Sample T-Test Results

Variable	Mean Pretest	Mean Posttest	t-count	Sig. (p)	Category
Learning Motivation	62,4	82,7	-9,215	0,000	Signifikan
Learning Outcomes	58,6	85,2	-11,034	0,000	Signifikan

Based on the results of the paired sample t-test, a significance value (p-value) of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) was obtained for both variables, namely learning motivation and learning outcomes. This indicates a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores. Therefore, it can be concluded that the implementation of the peer tutoring learning model significantly impacts student motivation and learning outcomes.

The relatively large t-test value and very small significance value ($p < 0.05$) indicate that the improvement was not due to chance but rather a result of the implementation of the peer tutoring learning model. Furthermore, the N-gain value, which is in the moderate to high category, indicates that this model is quite effective in improving student motivation and learning outcomes. Therefore, statistically, the peer tutoring learning model has a significant and positive impact on improving learning motivation and learning outcomes for chemistry education students in the early stages of their studies.

B. Discussion

The results of this study indicate that the implementation of the peer tutoring learning model significantly improved the learning motivation and learning outcomes of chemistry education students. This improvement is evident in the N-gain values for motivation (0.54) and learning outcomes (0.64), and is supported by statistically significant results ($p < 0.05$). These findings are consistent with various recent studies confirming that peer tutoring is an effective learning strategy in higher education contexts. The improvement in student learning motivation in this study can be explained through the social interaction approach that is at the core of the peer tutoring model. In this process, students actively engage in discussions, share insights, and provide academic support to one another. Recent research has shown that peer tutoring significantly improves students' learning motivation and independent learning abilities, particularly in first-year students who are still adapting to academic life. Furthermore, participation in a peer tutoring program has also been shown to increase students' self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation compared to students who do not participate in the program (Nardacchione & Peconio, 2022; Roscoe & Chi, 2007).

Improvements in motivational indicators such as attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction demonstrate that this model comprehensively addresses the motivational dimensions of learning. This aligns with the ARCS approach, where learning involving active interaction and hands-on experience has been shown to significantly increase student engagement. Recent experimental studies have also shown that peer-tutored learning can enhance learning motivation through greater emotional and social engagement (Metekohy et al., 2022).

From a learning outcome perspective, improved posttest scores indicate that peer tutoring is effective in enhancing conceptual understanding. This can be explained through the learning-by-teaching mechanism, where students acting as tutors experience cognitive reinforcement when explaining material to their peers. Meanwhile, students acting as tutees receive explanations in simpler, more easily understood language. Recent meta-analyses have shown that peer tutoring programs have a significant positive effect on improving students' academic performance in higher education. In fact, experimental studies have shown that students participating in peer tutoring programs can achieve significantly higher academic achievement than control groups.

Furthermore, peer tutoring also contributes to improving students' independent learning skills and study habits. A 2024 study showed that peer tutoring programs significantly improved students' self-directed learning and study habits ($p < 0.05$), which are important factors in long-term academic success. This is relevant to the results of this study, where students showed improvements not only in grades but also in active engagement in the learning process.

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From a theoretical perspective, the results of this study can be explained through Vygotsky's social constructivism theory, which posits that learning occurs through social interaction and assistance from more competent peers. In the context of peer tutoring, students act as scaffolding, helping their peers reach their zone of proximal development. Recent research also shows that interactions between students in peer tutoring significantly increase student engagement, critical thinking skills, and personal development.

Furthermore, the peer tutoring approach has been shown to improve students' attention and focus on learning. Recent experimental studies have shown that peer influence can increase learning attention and cognitive engagement, ultimately impacting learning outcomes. This supports the finding that the attention indicator of learning motivation experienced a significant increase in this study.

However, despite the significant increase, the moderate N-gain value indicates that the effectiveness of the peer tutoring model can still be improved. Several influencing factors include the quality of the peer tutor, the learning design, and the intensity of interaction during the learning process. Research indicates that the effectiveness of peer tutoring will be optimal if the tutor receives specialized training and adequate supervision.

Overall, the results of this study reinforce findings in recent literature that the peer tutoring learning model is an effective strategy for improving student motivation and learning outcomes. This model impacts not only cognitive aspects but also affective and social aspects of students. Therefore, the implementation of peer tutoring is highly recommended, especially for early-stage students, as an effort to improve the quality of learning in higher education.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research and analysis conducted, it can be concluded that the implementation of the peer tutoring learning model is effective in improving the learning motivation and learning outcomes of chemistry education students in the early stages of their studies. This is indicated by an increase in the average learning motivation score from 62.4 to 82.7 with an N-gain value of 0.54 (moderate category). In addition, student learning outcomes also increased from an average of 58.6 to 85.2 with an N-gain value of 0.64 (moderate-high category). The results of statistical tests indicate a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores for both motivation and learning outcomes ($p < 0.05$), thus indicating that the peer tutoring learning model has a positive and significant effect on improving both variables. This increase occurs because the peer tutoring model is able to create a collaborative learning atmosphere, increase interaction between students, and encourage active involvement in the learning process. Thus, the peer tutoring learning model can be used as an alternative effective learning strategy, especially for students in the early stages of their studies who are still adapting to the academic environment. There is an increase in chemistry learning outcomes for class XI students in high school by using the method practicum as evidenced by the acquisition of t count data of $10,321 > t$ table.

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